

PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF IMPROVING METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS FOR INTEGRATIVE TEACHING

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Abstract. *The integration of teaching and upbringing is becoming a fundamental regularity and a leading trend in the process of improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers for integrative instruction. This phenomenon has become a distinctive feature of vocational education pedagogy in the context of implementing a competency-based approach.*

Keywords: *anthropocentric orientation, pedagogical integration, interdisciplinary integration, concept of systems synthesis, thinking and critical approach, vitagenic teaching concept.*

Analysis of sources shows that the main feature of pedagogical integration is its **anthropo-orientation** (human orientation): a person is the subject and goal of pedagogical integration, its absolute system-forming factor. He creates integration, directs it and ensures its development. Regardless of the level and form of pedagogical activity, the final result of integration leads to qualitative changes in the process of socialization of the individual, that is, in the process of improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for integrative teaching.

As a result of the study of sources, we came to the following conclusions:

1. In scientific, including scientific-pedagogical literature, a sufficiently rich experience has been accumulated in studying integration problems, which makes it possible to analyze the regularities of developing the integration of teaching and upbringing in the vocational education system.

2. Despite the large number of integrative-pedagogical studies, their overall effectiveness is not high enough. The reasons are as follows:

o Works that mainly meet the direct requirements of practice predominate, which reduces their scientific significance.

o The main part of the studies (60–65%) is devoted to the substantive integration of the educational process and integrated forms of teaching; 25–30% to issues of institutional synthesis; the remaining 5–10% relate to other integrative problems, including the integration of teaching and upbringing.

o Among integrative-pedagogical concepts, two main groups are distinguished:

o Group 1:

o These are concepts that directly include integration processes in their content, and this is clearly expressed in their names. These include the following concepts:

o The concept of integration of the educational forces of society (V.D. Semenov, Yu.S. Brodsky);

- o The concept of interdisciplinary integration of pedagogical knowledge (V.I. Zagvyazinsky);
- o The concept of an integrative landscape of education (G.N. Serikov);
- o The concept of synthesis of textbook systems (L.A. Artemyeva, V.V. Gavrilyuk, M.I. Makhmutov);
- o The concept of integration of general and vocational education (M.A. Berulava, Yu.S. Tyunnikov);
- o The concept of integration of the content of primary vocational education (L.D. Fedotova);
- o The concept of integration of chemistry, chemical technology and materials science (I.K. Kuramshin);
- o The concept of integration and differentiation of forms of education (G.I. Ibragimov);
- o The concept of integration of higher education and fundamental sciences;
- o The concept of integrated educational institutions (USA, Western Europe).

- o **2-group:**

- o These include educational concepts in which the integrative element is not directly reflected, but is present as a result of their general description. These include:

- o The concept of the cultural and educational center (A.Ya. Nayn and others);
- o The concept of life-based (vitagen) education (A.S. Belkin);
- o The concept of the whole school in German pedagogy (R. Winkel).

- o **The most relevant concepts for our research:**

- o The concept of integrating the educational forces of society;
- o The concept of life-experience-based (vitagen) education.
- o A.S. Belkin's concept of vitagenic education:
 - o This concept takes the category of human life as the main methodological point of view. This implies the use of the rich resources of human activity in the implementation of educational tasks. At the same time, the goal of vocational schools is to develop the "life-affirming" qualities of future specialists, namely:

- o confidence in life;
- o understanding the meaning of life;
- o education of will;
- o joy and cheerfulness;
- o self-preservation and self-management skills are formed.

- o These, in turn, serve to improve the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for integrative teaching.

- o In addition, the integrative nature of the concept of vitagenic teaching is determined by its second main category - holography. **Holography** (from the Greek holos - whole, complete) is based on the concept of holism, the main formula of which is:

“The whole is greater than the sum of its parts.”

The integrative essence of the Vitagen education concept:

In this concept, all aspects of human activity (knowledge, skills, values, experience, emotions, motivation, etc.) are mastered in an interconnected manner. This turns the educational process into a process that performs the tasks of:

- not only imparting knowledge,

- but also forming and enriching the person's life experience,
- self-awareness,
- preparing for independent decision-making in preparation for professional activity.

With this approach, a person:

- understands his social and professional roles;
- determines his place in society;
- learns to plan his activities based on both individual and social interests.

The main tasks of pedagogical integration are:

- 1. Ensuring the continuity of knowledge and practice;**
- 2. Harmonizing professional and social competencies;**
- 3. Creating a unified system of teaching and upbringing;**
- 4. Ensuring individual development based on the personal capabilities of students.**

Also, with the help of pedagogical integration:

- knowledge is systematized;
- flexibility of thinking is formed;
- skills in solving problem situations in professional activities are developed;
- the level of professional self-awareness of students is increased.

In conclusion, it can be said that, The concept of vitagen education is considered one of the universal and effective approaches for modern pedagogy, especially in improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for integrative teaching.

Also, the integrative nature of the concept of vitagen education requires the integration of all components of pedagogical activity: goal, content, form, methods and means into a single system. In this system:

- the goal of personal development serves as the main goal;
- the content of the subject is understood as a means of personal development;
- forms and methods of education are selected on the basis of methods that are based on activity and take into account the individual experience of the student.

The main principles of pedagogical integration are:

• **The principle of person-centeredness.** This principle implies an individual approach to each student, taking into account his needs and capabilities.

• **The principle of activity and independence.** Active participation of the student in educational activities, development of independent thinking and decision-making skills.

• **The principle of experience-based learning.** Theoretical knowledge is directly related to practical activity.

• **The principle of reflection.** The student constantly evaluates his own activities and development.

Thus, the vitagen educational approach ensures the highest level of pedagogical integration, namely:

- a single content-competence structure of the knowledge system,
- professional and social development of the individual,
- the process of enrichment of personal experience.

As a result, the improvement of the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for integrative teaching takes place as a single process of education and upbringing, which is inextricably linked.

The integrative essence of the Vitagen concept of education is that it involves not only the formation of a system of knowledge and skills, but also the social and professional development of the individual. This approach serves to develop the individual's:

- self-awareness,
- independent decision-making,
- a sense of responsibility for the results of his or her activities.

Vitagen teaching also creates the following pedagogical opportunities:

- linking knowledge to real situations in life and professional activities;
- expanding and enriching personal experience;
- developing independent thinking and critical thinking skills;
- increasing the level of psychological and social readiness for professional activity.

In addition, this approach creates a wide opportunity for the formation of such components of competence as:

- **cognitive (knowledge),**
- **motivational**
- **axiological (values),**
- **practical (practical skills and experience),**
- **emotional-volitional (volitional and emotional self-control).**

In conclusion, the concept of vitagen education is a powerful pedagogical tool that ensures the integration of teaching and upbringing in improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for integrative teaching. This approach ensures the process of preparing a person for professional activity not only at the level of knowledge and skills, but also on the basis of his personal qualities and social adaptability.

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